

**ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY OF THE EXPRESSION OF THE
PROLIFERATIVE ACTIVITY OF KI-67 AND P53 IN OVARIAN TISSUE
SAMPLES FROM WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE WITH
MANIFESTATIONS OF INFERTILITY AND OBESITY**

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Annotation The attention of clinicians should be paid not only to the restoration of reproductive function, but also to the treatment of endometrial hyperplastic processes and metabolic changes. Despite the fact that the oncological aspects of polycystic ovary syndrome have been known for a long time, the problem of prevention and differentiated therapy, taking into account modern ideas about endocrine and metabolic disorders, remains relevant not only in the medical, but also in the social aspect and requires further research.

Keywords: polycystic ovary syndrome, infertility, hyperplastic processes

Abstract Molecular biological markers of hyperplastic processes are proliferative components of human cells and tissues. Therefore, research into molecular biological markers of proliferation is carried out in such areas as early diagnosis of proliferative processes, prognosis of hyperplasia, identification of circulating proliferative cells or markers, assessment of the prevalence of the process, detection of risk factors and making a clinical prognosis of the proliferative process. Currently, the complex of laboratory studies, in addition to classical morphological methods, includes immunohistochemical ones with the identification of molecular genetic markers, which has expanded the capabilities of clinical medicine in the treatment and prediction of hyperplastic processes in gynecology.

Research aim. To study the expression of the proliferative activity of Ki-67 and p53 in ovarian tissue samples from women of fertile age with manifestations of infertility and obesity

Materials and methods of research. To assess the proliferative activity (PA) of tissue, the number of Ki-67-positive cells per 200*300 tumor cells was calculated. The Ki-67 index was determined by the formula: $PA = \frac{\text{number of Ki-67 positive cells} \times 100}{\text{total number of cells}}$. PA markers were assessed based on the most commonly used assessment method: 0-20% - low PA, 21-50% - moderate, 51-100% - high

Equal groups of women with polycystic ovary syndrome were selected. Histological and immunohistochemical examination of the material together allows us to obtain a morphological description of the process, an assessment of the level of proliferation and apoptosis, an assessment of the level of expression of various receptors, which provides an accurate assessment of the further development and prognosis of the pathological process.

Results and discussions

In an IHC study in polycystic ovary syndrome, moderate expression of the proliferative activity of p53 is observed in 33% of women, negative in 67% of cases. Thus, moderate expression of Ki-67 is observed in 68% of women, high in 18% of women, and negative in 21% of cases. This marker is a marker of proliferation and is expressed in almost all phases of the mitotic cycle, and reflects the size of the proliferative pool, which proves the predominance of proliferative processes in polycystic ovary syndrome. As for the expression of the apoptosis marker, moderate and negative expression of mtp 53 was most often detected.

Based on the above, it becomes obvious that the attention of clinicians should be paid not only to the restoration of reproductive function, but also to the treatment of endometrial hyperplastic processes and metabolic changes. Despite the fact that the oncological aspects of polycystic ovary syndrome have been known for a long

time, the problem of prevention and differentiated therapy, taking into account modern ideas about endocrine and metabolic disorders, remains relevant not only in the medical, but also in the social aspect and requires further research.

Conclusion

Proliferative potential has been identified in polycystic ovary syndrome with infertility and obesity, the consideration of which has important diagnostic and prognostic significance. The importance of immunohistochemical markers reflecting the functional state of proliferative cells, which is important in assessing the characteristics of the course and outcome of the disease. Thus, our data show that there is an unfavorable course of the disease due to the expression of proliferation factors Ki-67 and apoptosis p53